

Synthesis, characterization and oxo-transfer kinetics of oxomolybdenum(IV) complexes with two tridentate ONS donor Schiff base ligands derived from benzoylacetone and *S*-benzyl/*S*-methyl dithiocarbazate

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Abstract : Six new oxomolybdenum(IV) complexes with tridentate dianionic ONS chelating ligands (H_2L^1 and H_2L^2) obtained by condensation of *S*-benzyl and *S*-methyl dithiocarbazate with benzoyl acetone have been synthesized. The complexes $[Mo^{IV}OL]_n$ and $[Mo^{IV}OL(N-N)]$, [where N-N = 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy) and 1,10-phenanthroline (*o*-phen)], were prepared from the corresponding $[Mo^{VI}O_2L]$ complexes by oxoabstraction with PPh_3 in absence/presence of bipy or *o*-phen. All complexes have been characterized by various spectroscopic techniques (IR, UV-Vis, 1H NMR), magnetic susceptibility measurements at room temperature and cyclic voltammetry. Cyclic voltammograms of these complexes exhibit irreversible oxidative as well as reductive responses centered on the metal. Kinetics of the oxo-transfer process from Me_2SO to $[MoO]^{2+}$ core of the complexes were studied spectrophotometrically in CH_2Cl_2 and DMF. Both $[Mo^{IV}OL]_n$ and $[Mo^{IV}OL(DMF)]$ react with the substrate Me_2SO in a two step process. The first step involves the equilibrium formation of a Me_2SO adduct, while in the second step, an intra-molecular oxo-transfer occurs from Me_2SO to the $[MoO]^{2+}$ core with the elimination of Me_2S .

Keywords : Oxomolybdenum(IV) complexes, cyclic voltammetry, oxoabstraction, oxo-transfer kinetics.

Introduction

Chemistry of molybdenum, the only second row transition element present in the living systems being intimately involved in some important bio-chemical processes through several oxido-reductase molybdoenzymes¹⁻³, is developed around such biological aspects as well as numerous industrially important chemical reactions⁴⁻⁷. Again, it has to be mentioned that molybdenum chemistry is dominated by its oxocations, $[MoO_2]^{2+}$ core and $[MoO]^{2+}$ among which the $[MoO]^{2+}$ species is much less stable than $[MoO_2]^{2+}$. Though catalytic role of compounds containing $[MoO_2]^{2+}$ species and their oxo-transfer

properties are widely studied, oxoacceptor capacity of Mo^{IV} compounds containing the $[MoO]^{2+}$ core are rather scantily studied, specially from kinetic point of view. Stable oxomolybdenum(IV) complexes are comparatively much less stable than their dioxomolybdenum(VI) counterparts and structurally characterized oxomolybdenum(IV) complexes are quite rare. In the present study, we report the synthesis, characterization, electrochemistry as well as kinetics of oxo-transfer reactions undergone by some of these oxomolybdenum(IV) complexes of two tridentate ONS chelating ligands^{8,9} which can exist in both keto and enol forms and form metal complexes in the enol

Scheme 1. Tautomeric keto and enol forms of the Schiff base ligands.

form (Scheme 1).

The complexes of the form $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]_n$ and $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}(\text{N-N})]$, where N-N = bipy and *o*-phen, were obtained by reacting the corresponding dioxo-molybdenum(VI) precursor reported previously by our group⁸⁻¹¹. Electrochemical activities of these complexes reveal the redox behavior of the Mo^{IV} center. The tridentate binegative chelating ligands in this work usually form complexes like $[\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{O}_2\text{L}]$ or $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]$ possessing one or two open coordination sites that can be utilized for substrate binding and subsequent atom transfer.

It is known that molybdenum(IV) and (V) oxidation states can be stabilized by the binding of a neutral bidentate co-ligand at the vacant sites of $[\text{MoO}]^{2+}$ moiety¹². The Mo^{IV} complexes with a $[\text{MoO}]^{2+}$ core are generally synthesized from the corresponding $[\text{MoO}_2]^{2+}$ complexes through oxoabstraction in dry nitrogen atmosphere using PPh_3 in the absence or presence of neutral N-N bidentate donors¹³. This oxo-transfer process is a simple bimolecular reaction involving the interaction between one $[\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{O}_2\text{L}]$ and one PPh_3 molecule. The activated complex so formed leads to the transfer of an oxygen atom by donating a lone pair of electrons of (alkyl/aryl substituted) phosphorus into the anti-bonding $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ π^* orbital which in turn forms the P-O bond and Mo^{IV} oxo complex with a $4d^2_{xy}$ configuration. So the oxo-transfer reaction may be considered as a two electron redox/oxygen-atom transfer (OAT) process.

Experimental

Materials :

$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2]$ was prepared as described in the literature¹⁴. Reagent grade solvents were dried and distilled prior to use. All other chemicals used for preparative work were of reagent grade, available commercially and used without further purification.

Synthesis of Schiff base ligands H_2L^1 and H_2L^2 :

S-Benzyl- β -N-(1-benzoyl)-2-propylidene dithiocarbazate (H_2L^1) :

A mixture of 10 mL (0.2 mol) hydrazine hydrate and 11.2 g (0.2 mol) KOH in 70 mL of 90% ethanol was cooled down to -10°C . 15 mL (0.25 mol) of CS_2 was added dropwise with constant stirring. The yellow oil which had formed was separated and dissolved in 60 mL of previously cooled 40% ethanol. To this, 23 mL (0.2 mol) of benzyl chloride was added slowly with vigorous stirring. The white product which formed was collected and after recrystallization from benzene was dissolved in 50 mL of absolute ethanol. To this solution, 32.4 g (0.2 mol) of benzoylacetone in 50 mL ethanol was added. The resulting mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature. The crystals which settled down were filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*. Yield ~80%; m.p. $\sim 120^\circ\text{C}$. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ (%): C, 63.16; H, 5.26; N, 8.19. Found: C, 62.19; H, 5.53; N, 7.89; IR (KBr pellet) cm^{-1} : $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ 3025(w), $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ 3357(s), $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ 1627(s), $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ 1315(s); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) :

$\left(\text{H}_3\text{C}-\underset{|}{\text{C}}=\text{N}-\right)$ 2.46 s (3H), (-S-CH₂-) 4.36 s (2H), (-CH) 6.48 s (1H), (-NH-) 12.1 s (1H), (-OH) 12.26 s (1H), (aromatic protons) 7.20–7.33 m (10H).

S-Methyl- β -N-(1-benzoyl)-2-propylidene dithiocarbamate (H_2L^2) :

The ligand H_2L^2 was prepared by following similar procedure using 12.5 mL (0.2 mol) of methyl iodide instead of benzyl chloride. Yield ~ 80%; m.p. 98 °C. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₄N₂S₂O (%) : C, 54.14; H, 5.26; N, 10.53. Found : C, 54.11; H, 4.95; N, 10.31; IR (KBr pellet) cm⁻¹ : $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ 3037(w), $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ 3289(s), $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ 1625(s), $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ 1310(m); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : $\left(\text{H}_3\text{C}-\underset{|}{\text{C}}=\text{N}-\right)$ 2.42 s (3H), (-S-CH₃) 4.38 s (3H), (-CH) 6.02 s (1H), (-NH-) 12.11 s (1H), (-OH) 12.2 s (1H), (aromatic protons) 7.18–7.32 m (5H).

Synthesis of MoOL complexes :

MoOL¹ (**1**) : To a filtered solution of 0.468 g (1.0 mmol) of [MoO₂L¹] in 20 mL dry degassed acetonitrile was added 0.393 g (1.5 mmol) of PPh₃ in 15 mL of dry degassed acetonitrile under purified dinitrogen and refluxed. The red solution turned dark brown and a brown compound separated within 30 min, filtered and washed with acetonitrile and dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous CaCl₂. Yield ~ 75%. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₆N₂S₂O₂Mo (%) : C, 47.78; H, 3.54; N, 6.19; Mo, 21.24. Found : C, 47.52; H, 3.20; N, 5.98; Mo, 20.86; UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂) [$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ (ε/dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 264 (3490), 422 (3260), 670 (1680); IR (KBr pellet) cm⁻¹ : $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ 1523(vs), $\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ 973(vs), $\nu_{\text{Mo-S}}$ 495(m), $\nu_{\text{Mo-N}}$ 576(m); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : $\left(\text{H}_3\text{C}-\underset{|}{\text{C}}=\text{N}-\right)$ 2.41 s (3H), (-S-CH₂-) 4.38 s (2H), (-CH) 6.37 s (1H), (aromatic protons) 7.22–7.46 m (10H).

MoOL² (**2**) : This compound was prepared similarly using 0.392 g (1.0 mmol) of MoO₂L². Yield ~ 70%. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₂N₂S₂O₂Mo (%) : C, 38.29; H, 3.19; N, 7.44; Mo, 25.53. Found : C, 37.75; H, 3.20; N, 7.13; Mo, 25.20; UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂) [$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ (ε/dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 260 (10810), 323 (4630), 416 (5040), 669 (510); IR (KBr pellet) cm⁻¹ : $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ 1525(vs), $\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ 968(vs), $\nu_{\text{Mo-S}}$ 496(w), $\nu_{\text{Mo-N}}$ 575(m); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : $\left(\text{H}_3\text{C}-\underset{|}{\text{C}}=\text{N}-\right)$ 2.41 s (3H), (-S-CH₃) 4.38 s (3H), (-CH) 6.37 s (1H), (aromatic protons) 7.22–7.46 m (5H).

Synthesis of MoOL(N-N) complexes :

Complexes (**3-6**) were prepared under dry N₂ atmosphere by refluxing the parent compounds [Mo^{VI}O₂L] with bipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline and PPh₃ having a mole ratio 1 : 10 : 1.5 in dry degassed CH₂Cl₂ for ~ 1–2 h. The green solutions formed were poured into *n*-hexane whereupon green solid separated, filtered, washed with CH₂Cl₂ and dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous CaCl₂. Yield ~ 70–75%.

MoOL¹(bipy) (**3**) : Anal. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₄N₄S₂O₂Mo (%) : C, 55.26; H, 3.95; N, 9.21; Mo, 15.79. Found : C, 54.92; H, 3.75; N, 9.10; Mo, 15.52; UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂) [$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ (ε/dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 255 (10050), 311 (7350), 394 (5340), 671 (200); IR (KBr pellet) cm⁻¹ : $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ 1596(vs), $\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ 913(vs), $\nu_{\text{Mo-S}}$ 433(m), $\nu_{\text{Mo-N}}$ 618(m); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : $\left(\text{H}_3\text{C}-\underset{|}{\text{C}}=\text{N}-\right)$ 2.41 s (3H), (-S-CH₂-) 4.38 s (2H), (-CH) 6.38 s (1H), (aromatic protons) 7.22–7.46 m (10H), 7.77–8.64 m (8H).

MoOL²(bipy) (**4**) : Anal. Calcd. for C₂₂H₂₀N₄S₂O₂Mo (%) : C, 49.62; H, 3.76; N, 10.53; Mo, 18.05. Found : C, 50.13; H, 3.80; N, 10.21; Mo, 17.87; UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂) [$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ (ε/dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 306 (3100), 323 (4630), 416 (3070), 671 (590); IR (KBr pellet) cm⁻¹ : $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ 1564(vs), $\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ 965(s), $\nu_{\text{Mo-S}}$ 435 (m), $\nu_{\text{Mo-N}}$ 576(m); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : $\left(\text{H}_3\text{C}-\underset{|}{\text{C}}=\text{N}-\right)$ 2.42 s (3H), (-S-CH₃) 5.69 s (3H), (-CH) 6.37 s (1H), (aromatic protons) 7.20–7.43 m (5H), 7.73–8.58 m (8H).

MoOL¹(*o*-phen) (**5**) : Anal. Calcd. for C₃₀H₂₄N₄S₂O₂Mo (%) : C, 56.96; H, 3.79; N, 8.86; Mo, 15.19. Found : C, 55.85; H, 3.25; N, 8.62; Mo, 15.03; UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂) [$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ (ε/dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 272 (19440), 320 (11800), 397 (5920), 666 (2480); IR (KBr pellet) cm⁻¹ : $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ 1518(s), $\nu_{\text{Mo=O}}$ 918(s), $\nu_{\text{Mo-S}}$ 427(m), $\nu_{\text{Mo-N}}$ 541(w); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : $\left(\text{H}_3\text{C}-\underset{|}{\text{C}}=\text{N}-\right)$ 2.69 s (3H), (-S-CH₂-) 4.31 s (2H), (-CH) 6.12 s (1H), (aromatic protons) 7.16–7.44 m (10H), 7.76–8.52 m (8H).

MoOL²(*o*-phen) (**6**) : Anal. Calcd. for C₂₄H₂₀N₄S₂O₂Mo (%) : C, 51.79; H, 3.59; N, 10.07; Mo, 17.27. Found : C, 51.39; H, 3.46; N, 9.84; Mo, 16.98; UV-Vis (CH₂Cl₂) [$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ (ε/dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)] : 265 (18250), 308 (12760), 395 (4740), 669 (920); IR

(KBr pellet) cm^{-1} : $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ 1518(s), $\nu_{\text{Mo}=\text{O}}$ 914(vs), $\nu_{\text{Mo}-\text{S}}$ 427(m), $\nu_{\text{Mo}-\text{N}}$ 554(w); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) : $\left(\text{H}_3\text{C}-\underset{|}{\text{C}}=\text{N}-\right)$ 2.69 s (3H), (-S-CH₃) 5.71 s (3H), (-CH) 6.14 s (1H), (aromatic protons) 7.15–7.46 m (5H), 7.74–8.48 m (8H).

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 240 C, H, N analyzer. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker 300 L NMR spectrometer operating at 300 MHz with TMS as internal standard. IR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer model 883 infrared spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra and data for kinetic study were recorded on a HITACHI U-3501 UV-Vis recording spectrophotometer. The kinetic measurements were performed under Argon atmosphere. Approximately, 2×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} solutions of Mo^{IV} complexes in $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{DMF}$ were employed. Pseudo-first order condition was maintained throughout by the use of an excess Me_2SO over the molybdenum concentration. All computation work for analyses of kinetic data were performed using Origin 6.0 software. Magnetic susceptibility was measured with a PAR model 155 vibrating sample magnetometer with $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant. Electrochemical data were collected on a Sycopel model AEW2 1820 F/S instrument at 298 K using a Pt working electrode, Pt auxiliary electrode and SCE reference electrode. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded in DMF containing 0.1 M TBAP as supporting electrolyte.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization of the ligands :

The Schiff base ligands *S*-benzyl- β -*N*-(1-benzoyl)-2-propylidene dithiocarbazate (H_2L^1) and *S*-methyl- β -*N*-(1-benzoyl)-2-propylidene dithiocarbazate (H_2L^2) were prepared by condensing *S*-benzyl and *S*-methyl dithiocarbazates with benzoyl acetone in ethanol^{8,15}. The ligands were satisfactorily characterized by elemental analyses, IR and ^1H NMR data.

Synthesis and characterization of oxomolybdenum(IV) complexes :

The oxomolybdenum(IV) complexes of the general formula $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]_n$ (**1-2**) were prepared¹³ by refluxing the solution of appropriate $[\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{O}_2\text{L}]$ complex with PPh_3 in

1 : 1.5 molar proportions in dry degassed CH_3CN under dry nitrogen. The red solution turned brown and a brown solid separated out within 30 min which was filtered, washed several times with dry degassed CH_3CN and dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

The oxomolybdenum(IV) complexes $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}(\text{N-N})]$ (**3-6**) were prepared¹³ refluxing the solution of appropriate $[\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{O}_2\text{L}]$ complex with PPh_3 in the presence of 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline in 1 : 1.5 : 10 molar proportions in dry degassed CH_2Cl_2 for 1 h under dry nitrogen. The green solution so formed was poured into *n*-hexane whereupon green solids separated, filtered, washed with dry CH_2Cl_2 several times and dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

The $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]_n$ and $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}(\text{N-N})]$ complexes have been characterized on the basis of elemental analyses and other analytical data including solution conductance and magnetic susceptibility measurements. The molar conductivity data in 10^{-3} mol L^{-1} CH_2Cl_2 indicate that they are non electrolytes. The complexes are diamagnetic at room temperature as expected for a d^2 Mo^{IV} center^{13,16-18}. It is to be noted that most of the previously reported oxomolybdenum(IV) complexes also exhibit diamagnetic behavior¹⁹⁻²². All the complexes are amorphous solids, stable at room temperature and are readily soluble in alcohol, CH_2Cl_2 , CH_3CN , DMF and DMSO, but insoluble in water. The brown colored solution of **1** and **2** in DMSO gradually change to the red color of the parent $[\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{O}_2\text{L}]$ complexes with the simultaneous emission of Me_2S . This has been verified by comparing the electronic spectrum with that of the parent $[\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{O}_2\text{L}]$ complex. This observation indicate that the Mo^{IV} center abstract the oxo group from DMSO to regenerate the parent dioxo Mo^{VI} complex. All the Mo^{IV} complexes are satisfactorily characterized by IR, ^1H NMR, electronic spectra and cyclic voltammetric data. The kinetics of oxo-transfer reaction from Me_2SO to $[\text{MoO}]^{2+}$ core in CH_2Cl_2 and DMF were carried out spectrophotometrically.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the complexes (**1-6**) were recorded in dry dichloromethane and the spectral data of complexes are presented in Sections *Synthesis of MoOL complexes* and *Synthesis of MoOL(N-N) complexes*. Spectra of $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]_n$ and $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}(\text{N-N})]$ complexes exhibit several bands in the 671–260 nm range. The absorption maximum are located in the 450–416 nm range may be assigned to the thiolato $\text{S}(\text{p}\pi)\text{-Mo}(\text{d}\pi)$ LMCT transition^{13,16} caused by the promotion of an electron from the filled HOMO of primarily sulfur $\text{p}\pi$ character to the empty LUMO of molybdenum $\text{d}\pi$. Bands at 320–306 nm are assigned to the nitrogen to molybdenum and oxygen to molybdenum charge transfer transitions^{16,30} respectively. Bands below 306 nm are due to intra-ligand transitions. The complexes exhibit one low energy charge transfer absorption band around 670 nm, characteristic of the $[\text{MoO}]^{2+}$ core^{13,17,18}.

IR and ¹H NMR spectra :

Characteristic IR bands of the two ligands and the corresponding oxomolybdenum(IV) complexes are listed in Sections *Synthesis of Schiff base ligands H₂L¹ and H₂L²* and *Synthesis of MoOL complexes*. Both the ligands exhibit two broad bands of medium intensity in the 3357–3025 cm^{-1} region, the higher frequency are due to $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ mode while the lower ones are assigned to the $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ vibration²³. Two strong $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ bands around 1627 and 1625 cm^{-1} for the ligands H_2L^1 and H_2L^2 are red shifted to 1518–1596 cm^{-1} and 1519–1564 cm^{-1} respectively in the corresponding complexes indicating the coordination of azomethine nitrogen to the oxo Mo^{IV} center^{24,25}. A new band around 541–618 cm^{-1} region in the complexes is assigned to $\nu_{\text{Mo-N}}$ ^{23,26}. The complexes exhibit a medium intensity band around 427–496 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Mo-S}}$ ²⁷. A single strong band at 968–973 cm^{-1} for the $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]_n$ complexes and a similar band in the range 913–965 cm^{-1} for the $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}(\text{N-N})]$ complexes are attributed to $\nu_{(\text{Mo=O})\text{t}}$ ^{13,17,18} as opposed to the twin symmetric and antisymmetric stretching bands for the $[\text{MoO}_2]^{2+}$ moiety of the $[\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{O}_2\text{L}]$ precursors¹⁶. Coordination of bipy or *o*-phen to the $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}]^{2+}$ center lowers the $\nu_{(\text{Mo=O})\text{t}}$ stretching frequency considerably^{23,26,28}. It is likely that the $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]$ complexes are polymeric^{13,17,18}, probably through $\text{Mo}=\text{O}---\text{Mo}$ linkage. This is further supported by the presence of a medium inten-

sity band around 815 cm^{-1} which is characteristics of the $\text{Mo}=\text{O}---\text{Mo}$ species²⁹, which is absent in the spectra of $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}(\text{N-N})]$ complexes. It is to be noted that previously reported Mo^{IV} oxo complexes **1** and **2** are polymeric in nature; whereas the complexes **3-6** are monomeric in nature.

¹H NMR data for the ligands (H_2L^1 and H_2L^2) and their corresponding complexes (**1-6**) are summarized in Sections *Synthesis of Schiff base ligands H₂L¹ and H₂L²* and *Synthesis of MoOL complexes*. The signals at δ 12.26 and 12.10; δ 12.20 and 12.11 in the ¹H NMR spectra corresponding to O-H and N-H of the ligands H_2L^1 and H_2L^2 disappear in the complexes (**1-6**) as a result of complexation. The methylene protons of the ligand H_2L^1 and its corresponding complexes (**1**, **3** and **5**) appearing at δ 4.36 and 4.38; δ 4.38; 4.31 indicate that the *S*-benzyl sulfur is not involved in the coordination. The ten aromatic protons appear as multiplets within the range δ 7.20–7.33 for the ligand H_2L^1 . In the complexes **1**, **3** and **5**, ten, eighteen and eighteen aromatic protons appear as multiplets within the range δ 7.22–7.46 (10H), 7.22–7.46 (10H) and 7.77–8.64 (8H) and δ 7.16–7.44 (10H) and 7.76–8.52 (8H) respectively. Similar observation for all types of protons is noted in the case of ligand H_2L^2 and its corresponding complexes **2**, **4** and **6**.

Electrochemical properties :

The cyclic voltammograms of the molybdenum(IV) complexes (**1-6**) at a Pt-electrode were recorded in dry degassed DMF containing 0.1 M TBAP as the supporting electrolyte over a potential range of 0.0 to 1.5 V. The numerical data of all the Mo^{IV} complexes are presented in Table 1 and representative voltammograms are shown in Fig. 1. For $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]_n$ (**1**, **2**) and $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}(\text{N-N})]$ (**3-6**) complexes, an initial positive scan at a rate of 100 mV s^{-1} gives two irreversible oxidative responses in the range +0.31 to +0.78 V and +0.70 to +1.15 V, which are assigned to $\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}/\text{Mo}^{\text{V}}$ and $\text{Mo}^{\text{V}}/\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}$ ^{13,30,31} respectively. On scan reversal, this Mo^{VI} species exhibits two one-electron reductive responses around –0.37 to –0.67 V and –1.09 to –1.19 V corresponding to $\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}/\text{Mo}^{\text{V}}$ and $\text{Mo}^{\text{V}}/\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}$ processes^{13,16–18} respectively.

Study of reactivity and oxo-transfer kinetics from substrate to Mo^{IV} :

Complexes $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]_n$ and $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}(\text{N-N})]$ exhibit

Table 1. Cyclic voltammetric results^a (V vs SCE) for oxomolybdenum(IV) complexes at 298 K

Complexes	Mo ^{IV} /Mo ^V	Mo ^V /Mo ^{VI}	Mo ^{VI} /Mo ^V	Mo ^V /Mo ^{VI}
	<i>E</i> _{pa} (V)	<i>E</i> _{pa} (V)	<i>E</i> _{pc} (V)	<i>E</i> _{pc} (V)
MoOL ¹ (1)	+0.48	+0.79	-0.37	-1.19
MoOL ² (2)	+0.78	+1.15	-0.47	-1.13
MoOL ¹ (bipy) (3)	+0.40	+0.78	-0.53	-1.11
MoOL ² (bipy) (4)	+0.31	+0.70	-0.47	-1.09
MoOL ¹ (<i>o</i> -phen) (5)	+0.60	+0.91	-0.67	-1.17
MoOL ² (<i>o</i> -phen) (6)	+0.31	+0.80	-0.54	-1.11

^aSolvent : DMF (dry, degassed); supporting electrolyte : 0.1 M TBAP; solution strength : 10⁻³ M; electrode : platinum; reference electrode : SCE; scan rate : 100 mV s⁻¹.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of complex [MoOL²] (2) in DMF at 298 K.

oxygen atom transfer from DMSO. When these complexes are dissolved in DMSO or reacted with pyridine N-oxide, brown color of the solution gradually changes to red indicating oxo-transfer from DMSO/pyridine N-oxide to the monooxo [MoO]²⁺ center generating [Mo^{VI}O₂L] type complexes which are isolated and characterized. This reaction may be represented as,

Oxo accepting behavior of these complexes with consequent oxidation at the Mo-center from IV to VI, may be related to the oxo-transfer behavior of oxido-reductase enzymes which bring about a two electron reduction by the substrate by removing an oxo ligand.

The kinetics of oxo-transfer reactions of [Mo^{IV}OL]_n

Scheme 2. (a) in CH₂Cl₂ and (b) in DMF.

were carried out in CH_2Cl_2 and DMF by conventional spectrophotometry with variation of substrate concentration in the range 0.04 to 0.20 mol dm^{-3} [200 to 1000 times molar excess of Me_2SO over Mo^{IV} complexes] under pseudo-first order condition³². It is expected that the reactions of $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]_n$ with Me_2SO in CH_2Cl_2 and DMF solutions is a two-step oxygen atom transfer (OAT) reaction to yield $[\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{O}_2\text{L}]$ and Me_2S (Scheme 2a and 2b).

The present study has focused on the change of reactivity of the Mo^{IV} complex molecule with variation of solvents (donor vs non-donor). Spectrophotometric studies of the reaction reveal that there is a clear isobestic point in the range 390 – 394 nm for each of reaction of $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]$ with Me_2SO in CH_2Cl_2 and DMF using ligands H_2L^1 and H_2L^2 (Figs. 2a, 2b, 2c and 2d). The final spectra are identical with that of $[\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}\text{O}_2\text{L}]$ complexes. The

Fig. 2a. Spectral change in the reaction of $[\text{MoOL}^1]$ ($2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) with Me_2SO (0.20 mol dm^{-3}) in CH_2Cl_2 at 298 K .

observed rate constants (k_{obs}) at various Me_2SO concentrations were obtained from the slope of the linear plots ($r = 0.98$ – 0.99) of $\log(A_t - A_\infty)$ against t (symbols have their usual significance) (Table 2). Again, plots of observed rate (k_{obs}) vs $[\text{Me}_2\text{SO}]$ are shown in Figs. 3a and 3b. At lower concentration range of Me_2SO , the rate increases with increasing substrate concentration, but at sufficiently higher concentration, the oxo-transfer rates (k_{obs}) are virtually independent of $[\text{Me}_2\text{SO}]$ that is the substrate saturation kinetics is obtained.

Fig. 2b. Spectral change in the reaction of $[\text{MoOL}^2]$ ($2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) with Me_2SO (0.20 mol dm^{-3}) in CH_2Cl_2 at 298 K .

Fig. 2c. Spectral change in the reaction of $[\text{MoOL}^1]$ ($2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) with Me_2SO (0.08 mol dm^{-3}) in DMF at 298 K .

The reaction (Scheme 2a) reveals that the polymeric form of the complex $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]_n$ is in equilibrium with the sulfoxide-ligated complex $n[\text{MoOL}(\text{Me}_2\text{SO})]$ in CH_2Cl_2 solvent but the monomeric complex formed by the reaction of $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]$ with DMF which is in equilibrium with the complex $[\text{MoOL}(\text{Me}_2\text{SO})]$ (Scheme 2b). After the completion of the reaction, Mo^{IV} complexes are oxidized to Mo^{VI} complexes.

The oxygen atom transfer reaction from Me_2SO to $\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}$ in CH_2Cl_2 follows the rate law³² :

Fig. 2d. Spectral change in the reaction of $[\text{MoOL}^2]$ ($2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) with Me_2SO (0.08 mol dm^{-3}) in DMF at 298 K.

Table 2. Observed rate constants (k_{obs}) for oxo-transfer reaction of $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]$ ($2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) with Me_2SO in CH_2Cl_2 and DMF solvents at 298 K

Solvent	$[\text{Me}_2\text{SO}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	Rate constant	
		$[\text{MoOL}^1]$ ($10^2 \times k_{\text{obs}}$) (s^{-1})	$[\text{MoOL}^2]$ ($10^2 \times k_{\text{obs}}$) (s^{-1})
CH_2Cl_2	0.04	1.73 ± 0.08	1.80 ± 0.13
	0.08	3.37 ± 0.12	2.74 ± 0.32
	0.10	3.68 ± 0.15	3.29 ± 0.13
	0.12	3.76 ± 0.15	3.62 ± 0.18
	0.14	4.03 ± 0.26	3.77 ± 0.27
	0.16	4.30 ± 0.21	3.92 ± 0.16
	0.20	4.51 ± 0.18	4.15 ± 0.19
DMF	0.04	2.70 ± 0.10	2.50 ± 0.03
	0.08	3.80 ± 0.14	3.88 ± 0.03
	0.10	5.01 ± 0.16	4.36 ± 0.05
	0.12	5.55 ± 0.11	4.52 ± 0.05
	0.14	6.69 ± 0.08	5.57 ± 0.08
	0.16	6.83 ± 0.29	5.80 ± 0.06
	0.20	7.28 ± 0.23	6.15 ± 0.05

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{MoOL}(\text{Me}_2\text{SO})] = k_1 [\text{MoOL}][\text{Me}_2\text{SO}] \quad (1)$$

The eq. (1) gives the observed rate constants (k_{obs}) as,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_1 K [\text{Me}_2\text{SO}]}{1 + K [\text{Me}_2\text{SO}]} \quad (2)$$

The oxygen atom transfer reaction from Me_2SO to

Fig. 3a. Dependence of rate constant in the reaction of $[\text{MoOL}^1]$ ($2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in DMF at 298 K with concentration of Me_2SO (substrate).

Fig. 3b. Dependence of rate constant in the reaction of $[\text{MoOL}^1]$ ($2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in CH_2Cl_2 at 298 K with concentration of Me_2SO (substrate).

$[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}]$ in DMF follows the rate law³³ :

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [\text{MoOL}(\text{X})] = k_2 [\text{MoOL}(\text{Me}_2\text{SO})], \quad (3)$$

The eq. (3) yields the observed rate constant as,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_2 K [\text{Me}_2\text{SO}]}{K [\text{Me}_2\text{SO}] + [\text{DMF}]} \quad (4)$$

where, k_1 and k_2 are the oxo-transfer rate constants (Scheme 2a and 2b) in the reactions of $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}^1]$ and $[\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OL}^2]$ with Me_2SO in CH_2Cl_2 and DMF respec-

tively and K is the respective equilibrium constant.

The plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{Me}_2\text{SO}]$ give straight lines ($r \sim 0.99$) with finite intercepts and insignificant errors, from which k_1 and k_2 are determined from the reciprocal of the intercept and the respective equilibrium constants, K are evaluated from the ratio of intercept to slope³³ (Table 3).

Complex	Solvent			
	CH ₂ Cl ₂		DMF	
	k_1 (s ⁻¹)	K	k_2 (s ⁻¹)	K
[MoOL ¹]	0.0894	6.23	0.1278	83.90
[MoOL ²]	0.0658	9.41	0.0949	114.88

The rate constants k_1 and k_2 are of the same order for both the polymer [Mo^{IV}OL]_n and monomer [Mo^{IV}OL(DMF)] but comparing the K -values of polymeric and monomeric species, it is found that the values are smaller for the [MoOL(Me₂SO)] in CH₂Cl₂ than for the same in DMF. This is due to the fact that [MoOL(Me₂SO)] in CH₂Cl₂ is obtained from the breaking of polymer to monomer by Me₂SO coordination, while [MoOL(Me₂SO)] in DMF is generated through nucleophilic substitution.

Conclusion

Several mononuclear oxomolybdenum(IV) complexes [Mo^{IV}OL]_n and [Mo^{IV}OL(N-N)] have been synthesized and characterized by various physico-chemical techniques. However, mononuclear oxomolybdenum(IV) complexes of ONS donor ligands are not studied adequately, due to the difficulty involved in stabilizing the [MoO]²⁺ core.

The oxygen atom transfer from DMSO/pyridine N-oxide to monooxo Mo^{IV} species leads to the formation of dioxo Mo^{VI}. The rate constants of oxo-transfer reactions are of the same order for both the polymeric [Mo^{IV}OL]_n and monomeric [Mo^{IV}OL(DMF)] but the equilibrium constant K for the formation of the sulfoxide-ligated species is higher for [Mo^{IV}OL(DMF)] than for [Mo^{IV}OL]_n. Binegative ONS donor Schiff bases satisfy the +2 charge of the metal leading to the formation of the uncharged complexes, which are fairly stable and could be isolated

in the solid state. Bipyridine and *o*-phenanthroline further stabilize the [MoO]²⁺ core and prevent polymerization.

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